

**Report of Research Assessment Practices at Blanquerna
(Universitat Ramon Llull) in the last 20 years: 2004–2024.**

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Re-Ass project

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Review of Current Practices

Background

The Faculty of Psychology, Education and Sport Sciences (FPCEE) has a long-standing tradition of evaluating the research activity of its academic staff, beginning with the publication of its first evaluation criteria and procedures in October 2004. Evaluation—covering both teaching and research—is structured in three-year cycles. The first evaluation covered the period from September 2004 to August 2007, although internal circumstances delayed its actual implementation.

The process was reactivated following the May 2010 publication of the institutional framework for academic career progression. The evaluation period was extended to September 2010, and the assessment focused exclusively on faculty members with officially recognized research time in their contracts. In 2010, 58 faculty members were assessed: 51% received a positive evaluation, 30% negative, and 19% did not submit the required documentation.

In March 2013, a second round of evaluations was conducted using the same criteria, with an exemption introduced for those who had already undergone external evaluation by a recognized quality agency (e.g., doctoral defense, academic accreditation, or recognized research periods). Of the 69 eligible faculty members, 56% were evaluated positively, 22% negatively, and 22% were exempt. Additional evaluations were conducted in 2016 and 2019, maintaining similar procedures and yielding comparable results.

Unified Evaluation Criteria

In preparation for the 2024–2029 General Research Plan (*Pla General de recerca-PGR*) uniting the three Blanquerna faculties, a joint reflection process was initiated on how to evaluate academic research activity. While FPCEE had previously conducted four rounds of evaluation, the faculties of Health Sciences and of Communication and International Relations had not. The process began by reviewing other universities' models and was designed to align with the qualitative and quantitative standards used by quality assurance agencies to evaluate both researchers and research centers both in Catalonia and Spain. The primary goal was to establish common evaluation standards across the three faculties, while respecting the specificity of their academic disciplines.

Development Process

The work began in February 2021 with the Vice-Deans of Research from all three faculties. A preliminary draft was shared with the Directors of Research Institutes, amended accordingly, and then submitted for approval by the Blanquerna Research and Ethics Council (*Comissió d'Ètica i Recerca-CER*).

Though the PGR was not formally approved until January 2024, the CER agreed to pilot the new evaluation system at FPCEE in 2023, continuing the established three-year cycle. The pilot covered the period from October 1, 2019, to September 30, 2022. This pilot helped calibrate scoring thresholds for each contractual academic profile across faculties. Prior to launching the pilot, all research group leaders at the faculty were

briefed to clarify the new criteria. Once validated, the evaluation system was also implemented at the other two faculties.

Evaluation as a Quality Indicator

Research and quality are intrinsically linked. Research enhances methodological rigor, while quality assessment ensures that scientific production is appropriate and recognized. For the most recent evaluation, the process was jointly implemented by the Research Office and the Faculty's Quality Unit, to ensure alignment with the evaluation of teaching activities traditionally managed by the latter.

Purpose of the Evaluation

The assessment targeted faculty members with officially recognized research time. It aimed to stimulate research activity, support career development strategies, and maintain quality standards required by external agencies. Two secondary goals emerged:

- The need to provide evidence helped to uncover achievements not previously reported through regular channels (e.g., the MERIT platform or research funding tracking).
- The validation process allowed for pedagogical correction of misreported records.

The evaluation tool was also designed as a self-assessment instrument, allowing academics to measure their research achievements against their professional category's expectations, even though formal evaluations will continue to follow the three-year cycle.

Evaluation Criteria

The assessment was based on three categories:

- *Productivity* (60% weight): Impact-factor publications (JCR, SJR), books or chapters (SPI), other publications, dissemination activities (conference presentations, peer review, editorial boards), and contributions like doctoral supervision and patents.
- *Projects* (35%): Leadership or participation in competitive and non-competitive projects, with recognition also given to unsuccessful competitive proposals.
- *Other merits* (5%): Research group leadership and research stays (minimum one month).

A standardized form was created to collect personal data, quantitative metrics for each category, and qualitative tables to justify evidence submitted. Guidelines and templates accompanied the call.

Validation Process

Evaluation was also intended as a formative exercise. Alongside scores, individualized feedback addressed issues in submitted evidence. Validation was supported by technical staff from the Library Service (publications), Research Office (research projects), and Innovation and Transfer Office (transfer projects). A shared validation spreadsheet facilitated annotations and corrections.

Results

Only faculty members with recognized research time were required to participate; others could opt in voluntarily. A differentiated scoring threshold was applied based on contract type. In the latest call, 80 researchers participated, with 20% exempt due to external evaluation credentials. Of the remaining 64, 43% received a “very favorable” evaluation, 42% “favorable,” and 14% “unfavorable.”

Feedback

Each researcher received personalized feedback via email, including:

- Overall rating (very favorable, favorable, or not favorable)
- Score out of 100
- Average and score range for their academic category
- The scoring table for each evaluation parameter

Where applicable, feedback included detailed explanations of corrections and contact details for follow-up with the validating departments.

Documents and Tools Used

- Annex 1. Call for applications
- Annex 2. Evaluation form template
- Annex 3. Table completion guide
- Annex 4. Scoring table with categories, parameters, metrics, values, and caps
- Annex 5. Final scoring thresholds
- Annex 6. Individual evaluation report template

Assessment of Current Research Assessment Practices

Strengths

- 1. Institutionalization and Continuity***
 - A long-standing tradition of regular, structured evaluations (since 2004) has institutionalized assessment as part of academic culture.
 - The triennial cycle provides a consistent framework for faculty career development and accountability.
- 2. Structured and Transparent Procedures***
 - Defined criteria communicated through templates and guides ensures conceptual transparency.
 - Clear communication through individualized feedback and engagement of technical services ensures procedural transparency.
- 3. Integration of Quality Assurance Structures***
 - Collaboration between the Research Office and the Quality Unit strengthens coherence between teaching and research evaluations.
- 4. Recent Moves Towards Unification and Reflection***
 - Efforts to develop unified criteria across all faculties reflect institutional commitment to improving consistency.

5. ***Formative aim of the research evaluation***

- Feedback mechanisms offer developmental support for researchers, including correction of misreported evidence and learning opportunities.

Weaknesses

1. ***Heavy Dependence on Quantitative Indicators***

- High weight on bibliometric criteria (JCR/SJR, IF) and competitive funding metrics reinforces a productivity-based culture, contrary to CoARA principles.

2. ***Limited Recognition of Diverse Contributions***

- Other forms of impact (societal, collaborative, open science practices) are marginal or missing in the current framework.

3. ***Rigid Scoring Model***

- Top-down metrics (fixed scores, caps) may not accommodate disciplinary diversity or career stage differences, potentially disadvantaging early-career researchers or interdisciplinary work.

4. ***Partial Coverage***

- Only researchers with officially recognized research hours are evaluated mandatorily. This may exclude relevant contributions from other academics, hindering a holistic understanding of the institution's research landscape.

5. ***Limited Peer Involvement and Reflective Dialogue***

- While technical validation is robust, there is little indication of peer-review processes or reflexive discussion on what constitutes 'quality' research.

Opportunities

- ***Fostering Researcher Development:*** A new model can better support researchers' career progression, especially in under-recognized areas like collaborative, practice-based or societal research.
- ***Innovation and Inclusion:*** Creating new assessment tools (e.g., narrative CVs, open peer feedback, impact narratives) should help us to foster inclusion, innovation and recognize the complexity of research work.
- ***Interdisciplinary and Societal Impact Recognition:*** Expanding criteria can help reward activities central to Blanquerna's mission—engaged, transformative research in education, health, and communication.

Threats

- ***Resistance to Reform:*** Shifting away from long-established metric-based assessment may meet cultural or political resistance, especially from researchers benefiting from the current model.
- ***Credibility Gaps:*** Without robust communication and legitimacy-building efforts, the new system may be perceived as less objective or more discretionary.
- ***Loss of Benchmarking Ease:*** Moving from metric-based scores to qualitative evaluation may hinder comparisons at the institutional or external levels unless new tools are developed.

Synthesis of the Assessment

The current system at Blanquerna combines administrative robustness and historical continuity with a strong emphasis on quantitative, metric-based assessment. While it ensures procedural consistency and aligns with traditional quality assurance standards, it underrepresents the full diversity of scholarly contributions. It rewards a narrow definition of excellence, primarily favoring high-impact publications and competitive funding, with limited sensitivity to disciplinary differences, career stages, or alternative forms of impact. These limitations pose risks to fairness, inclusivity, and innovation. Moreover, while formative purposes were claimed to be crucial, the existing procedures, strategies, tools and mechanisms have resulted in limited evidence of how they promote researcher development.

Significant aspects of the Co-Ara principles proposed by Re-Ass have been absent of the research assessment practices (e.g. valuing qualitative assessment, peer review, narrative accounts, and a broader spectrum of research contributions). Considering the mentioned strengths of the current system, we should warrant careful navigation of cultural resistance, institutional coherence, and methodological clarity. The results for the SWOT analysis and the current practices assessment led us to identify the main challenges the ReAss project should address:

- ***Raising awareness of the Co-Ara principles as a new Assessment Culture:*** We aim to transitioning from quantification and rankings to reflective, qualitative assessments. We knew that this transition requires deep cultural change and strategic engagement. Re-Ass training and dissemination strategies must carefully address these requirements.
- ***Ensuring Fairness and Transparency:*** Qualitative assessment methods must be clearly justified and consistently applied to ensure perceived fairness. We are already working on new templates that can appropriately replace the existing ones (see Annexes)
- ***Accommodating Disciplinary and Career Diversity:*** This was a non-solved challenge in the existing model and current practices. The Re-Ass new model should provide mechanisms to remain sensitive to different research profiles while preserving shared standards.

Re-Ass dimensions of change

At the moment, we have established the following six dimensions of change that will structure the strategies and actions to develop in the pilot:

1. *Broaden the conceptualization of Research Quality*
The new proposal will foster the problematization of the concepts of research assessment and research quality by discussing the current systems assumptions, strengths and weaknesses and acknowledging diverse outputs and impact types, including community engagement, open science, interdisciplinary work, and knowledge transfer.
2. *Embed Peer Review and Narrative Assessment*
The new proposal will develop clear procedures and tools for qualitative, peer-based evaluation and introduce narrative CVs or portfolios tailored to Blanquerna's research fields.
3. *Ensure researcher development and inclusivity Across Career Stages*
The proposal will discuss with the researcher community at Blanquerna how to include flexible, transparent benchmarks that consider researcher development, supporting early-career researchers and non-traditional trajectories. At the same time, this dimension will discuss ways to address the tension between team and collaborative research work and individual development by considering the research activity structures and roles at Blanquerna and URL.
4. *Enhance Reflexivity and Transparency*
Similarly, the proposal will provide procedures to ensure formative feedback, dialogic assessment practices, and clear criteria to ensure legitimacy and trust.
5. *Foster Researcher Engagement and Co-Creation*
Ultimately, the proposal will sustain ongoing consultation and training with researchers to co-create the new criteria and raise awareness of the rationale behind the reform.
6. *Discuss the Role of Evaluation in Career Progression*
Though this is a long-term dimension of change that exceeds the Re-Ass objectives, we also want to start the discussion regarding how assessment outcomes influence recognition, research time allocation, and promotion within a framework consistent with CoARA.